

CHALLENGES FACING ADHOC NETWORKS Vs ROUTING

Dr.S.Brilly Sangeetha
Head of the Department ,
Department of CSE,IES College of Engineering
Chittilappilly, Thrissur,Kerala,India.

Abstract:

Adhoc networks are rapidly deployable, self configuring and known for existing infrastructure. It has Wireless links and the nodes are mobile, topology can be very dynamic. Nodes must be able to relay traffic since communicating nodes might be out of range. A MANET can be a standalone network or it can be connected to external networks(Internet).

Ad hoc networks are infrastructure Networks with fixed, wired backbone . Mobile communicates directly with access points . Suitable for locations where access points can be placed For eg) Cellular networks

Keywords Adhoc networks, Wireless links, MANET, Cellular networks

INTRODUCTION

1.1 ADHOC NETWORKS

Adhoc networks are Self-organizing and adaptive . It allows spontaneous formation and deformation of mobile networks . Each mobile host acts as a router and supports peer-to-peer communications .It reduces administrative cost and ease of deployment It's a network without any base stations “infrastructure-less” or multi-hop . A collection of two or more devices equipped with wireless communications and networking capability which supports anytime and anywhere computing . There are two topologies:

Heterogeneous (left)

- Differences in capabilities

Homogeneous or fully symmetric (Right)

- All nodes have identical capabilities and responsibilities Self-organizing and adaptive

1.2 OPERATING PRINCIPLE

Fig. depicts a peer-to-peer multihop ad hoc network where mobile node A communicates directly with B (single hop) when a channel is available . If Channel is not available, then multi-hop communication is necessary e.g. A->D->B . For multi-hop communication to work, the intermediate nodes should route the packet i.e. they should act as a router . Example: For communication between A-C, B, or D & E, should act as routers

Example of an Ad Hoc Network

1.3 BRINGING UP AN ADHOC NETWORK

1. Ad hoc network begins with at least two nodes broadcasting their presence (beaconing) with their respective address information
2. They may also include their location info if GPS equipped
3. Beaconing messages are control messages. If node A is able to establish a direct communication with node B verified by appropriate control messages between them, they both update their routing tables
4. Third node C joins the network with its beacon signal. Two scenarios are possible:

(i) A & B both try to determine if single hop communication is feasible

(ii) Only one of the nodes e.g. B tries to determine if single hop communication is feasible and establishes a connection

5. The distinct topology updates consisting of both address and the route updates are made in three nodes immediately. In first scenario, all routes are direct i.e. A->B, B->C, and A->C (Lets assume bi-directional links)

In the second scenario, the routes are updated

1. First between B & C,

2. then between B & A,

3. Then between B & C again confirming that A and C both can reach each other via B

1.4 TOPOLOGY UPDATE DUE TO A LINK FAILURE

Mobility of nodes may cause link breakage requiring route updates . Assume link between B & C breaks because of some reason . Nodes A & C are still reachable via D and E . So old route between A &C was A->B->C is to be replaced by A->D->E->C .All five nodes are required to

incorporate this change in their routing table . This change will happen first in nodes B & C .
Then A & E . Then D

II CHALLENGES FACING AD HOC NETWORKS

2.1 TRAFFIC CHARACTERISTICS

Traffic characteristics may differ in different ad hoc networks

- bit rate
- timeliness constraints
- reliability requirements
- unicast / multicast / geocast
- host-based addressing / content-based addressing / capability-based addressing

May co-exist (and co-operate) with an infrastructure-based network

2.2 TRAFFIC PROFILES

Three distinct types of traffic patterns observed in ad hoc networks

1. Peer-to-peer between two entities (Fig. a) – Bursty
2. Two or more devices in a group communication while moving as a group (correlated traffic)
-> remote to remote communication
3. Hybrid non-coherent communication among nodes -> uncorrelated traffic

2.3 CHALLENGES IN ADHOC NETWORKS

- Host is no longer an end system - can also be an acting intermediate system
- Changing the network topology over time
- Potentially frequent network partitions
- Every node can be mobile
- Limited power capacity
- Limited wireless bandwidth
- Presence of varying channel qualityNo centralized entity – distributed
- How to support routing ?
- How to support channel access?
- How to deal with mobility?
- How to conserve power?
- How to use bandwidth efficiently?

III PROBLEMS FACED IN ADHOC NETWORKS

3.1 PROBLEMS FACING ROUTING IN AD HOC NETWORKS

Routers are now moving and then link changes are happening quite often . There is packet losses due to transmission errors. Event updates are sent often – a lot of control traffic . Routing table may not be able for converge. Routing loop may exist and Current wired routing uses shortest path metric

3.2 PROBLEMS FACING CHANNEL ACCESS IN AD HOC NETWORKS

Distributed channel access, i.e. no fixed base station concept and very hard to avoid packet collisions.It is very hard to support QoS and the early work on packet radio is based on CSMA.

3.3 PROBLEMS OF MOBILITY IN AD HOC

Mobility affects signal transmission which in turn affects communication . Mobility affects channel access and routing . Mobility-induced route changes and packet losses . Mobility

affects multicasting and applications. Mobility patterns may be different to the people sitting at an airport lounge or New York taxi cabs or to kids playing or for military movements or in a personal area network . Mobility characteristics include

- speed
- predictability
- direction of movement
- pattern of movement
- uniformity (or lack thereof) of mobility characteristics among different nodes

3.4 PROBLEMS OF POWER IN AD HOC

Ad hoc devices come in many different forms . Most of them battery powered . Battery technology is not progressing as fast as memory or CPU technologies .Wireless transmission, reception, retransmission, beaconing, consume power. There is a quest for power-efficient protocols and better power management techniques

IV. ROUTING PROTOCOLS

4.1 TRADITIONAL ROUTING

A routing protocol sets up a routing table in routers.A node makes a local choice depending on global topology

ROUTING TABLE AT 1

Destination	Next hop	Destination	Next hop
1	—	7	2
2	2	8	2
3	3	9	2
4	3	10	2
5	2	11	3
6	2	12	3

4.2 DISTANCE VECTOR & LINK STATE ROUTING

Both assumes as if the router knows address of each neighbour and cost of reaching each neighbour .But allow a router to determine global routing and information by talking to its neighbours. Distance vector router knows the cost to each destination .Link state router knows entire network topology and computes shortest path Distance vector routing.

Example:Distance Vector

Example : Link state

4.3 ROUTING AND MOBILITY

Finding a path from a source to a destination. The main issues are frequent route changes
ie) amount of data transferred between route changes may be much smaller than traditional networks and route changes may be related to host movement The second issues is low bandwidth links. The goal of routing protocols is to decrease routing related overhead and finding short and stable routes.

Mobile IP

V. ROUTING IN ADHOC NETWORKS

5.1 UNICAST ROUTING PROTOCOLS

Many protocols have been proposed. Some specifically invented for MANET and others adapted from protocols for wired networks. No single protocol works well in all environments. Some attempts made to develop adaptive/hybrid protocols and standardization efforts in IETF such as MANET, MobileIP working groups

5.2 ROUTING PROTOCOLS

5.2.1 Proactive protocols

- Traditional distributed shortest path Protocols
- Maintain routes between every host pair at all times
- Based on periodic updates; High routing overhead
- Example: DSDV (destination sequenced distance vector)
- Always maintain routes
- Little or no delay for route determination
- Consume bandwidth to keep routes up to date
- Maintain routes which may never be used

5.2.2 Reactive protocols

- Determine route if and when needed
- Source initiates route discovery
- Example: DSR (dynamic source routing)
- Lower overhead since routes are determined on demand
- Significant delay in route determination
- Employ flooding (global search)

- Control traffic may be bursty
- Which approach achieves a better trade off depend on the traffic and mobility patterns

5.2.3 Hybrid protocols

- Adaptive; Combination of proactive and reactive
- Example : ZRP (zone routing protocol)

5.2 REACTIVE ROUTING PROTOCOLS

5.2.1 Dynamic Source Routing (DSR)

When node S wants to send a packet to node D, but does not know a route to D, node S initiates a route discovery .Source node S floods Route Request (RREQ) .Each node *appends own identifier* when forwarding RREQ

Route Discovery in DSR

- Node H receives packet RREQ from two neighbors:
potential for collision

Route Discovery in DSR

- Node C receives RREQ from G and H, but does not forward it again, because node C has **already forwarded RREQ** once

Route Discovery in DSR

- Nodes J and K both broadcast RREQ to node D
- Since nodes J and K are **hidden** from each other, their transmissions may collide

Route Discovery in DSR

- Node D **does not forward** RREQ, because node D is the **intended target** of the route discovery

Destination D on receiving the first RREQ, sends a Route Reply (RREP). RREP is sent on a route obtained by reversing the route appended to received RREQ. RREP includes the route from S to D on which RREQ was received by node D.

Route Reply in DSR

← Represents RREP control message

5.2.4 Dynamic Source Routing (DSR)

Node S on receiving RREP, caches the route included in the RREP. When node S sends a data packet to D, the entire route is included in the packet header hence the name source routing. Intermediate nodes use the source route included in a packet to determine to whom a packet should be forwarded

Packet header size grows with route length

5.2.5 Dynamic Source Routing: Advantages

- Routes maintained only between nodes who need to communicate reduces overhead of router maintenance.
- Route caching can further reduce route discovery overhead
- A single route discovery may yield many routes to the destination, due to intermediate nodes replying from local caches

5.2.6 Dynamic Source Routing: Disadvantages

Packet header size grows with route length due to source routing.

- Flood of route requests may potentially reach all nodes in the network.

- Potential collisions between route requests propagated by neighboring nodes and insertion of random delays before forwarding RREQ.
- Increased contention if too many route replies come back due to nodes replying using their local cache- Route Reply *Storm* problem.
- Stale caches will lead to increased overhead.

5.2.6 Location Aided Routing (LAR)

Exploits location information to limit scope of route request flood. Location information may be obtained using GPS. *Expected Zone* is determined as a region that is expected to hold the current location of destination. Expected region determined based on potentially old location information, and knowledge of the destination's speed. Route requests limited to a *Request Zone* that contains the Expected Zone and location of the sender node.

5.2.8 Request Zone

Define a Request Zone. LAR is same as flooding, except that only nodes in request zone forward route request. Smallest rectangle including S and expected zone for D.

Advantages

- reduces the scope of route request flood
- reduces overhead of route discovery

Disadvantages

- Nodes need to know their physical locations
- Does not take into account possible existence of obstructions for radio transmissions

5.2.9 Ad Hoc On Demand Distance Vector Routing (AODV)

DSR includes source routes in packet headers. Resulting large headers can sometimes degrade Performance particularly when data contents of a packet are small. AODV attempts to improve on DSR by maintaining routing tables at the nodes, so that data packets do not have to contain routes. AODV retains the desirable feature of DSR that routes are maintained only between nodes which need to communicate.

Route Requests (RREQ) are forwarded in a manner similar to DSR. When a node rebroadcasts a Route Request, it sets up a reverse path pointing towards the source and AODV assumes symmetric (bidirectional) Links. When the intended destination receives a Route Request, it replies by sending a Route Reply (RREP). Route Reply travels along the reverse path setup ,when Route Request is forwa

Route Requests in AODV

..... Represents transmission of RREQ

Route Requests in AODV

← Represents links on Reverse Path

Reverse Path Setup in AODV

- Node C receives RREQ from G and H, but does not forward it again, because node C has **already forwarded RREQ** once

Reverse Path Setup in AODV

Reverse Path Setup in AODV

• Node D does not forward RREQ, because node D is the intended target of the RREQ

Forward Path Setup in AODV

Forward links are setup when RREP travels along the reverse path

5.2.10 Route Request and Route Reply

Route Request (RREQ) includes the last known sequence number for the destination. An intermediate node may also send a Route Reply (RREP) provided that it knows a more recent path than the one previously known to sender. Intermediate nodes that forward the RREP, also record the next hop to destination. A routing table entry maintaining a reverse path is purged after timeout interval. A routing table entry maintaining a forward path is purged if *not used* for a *active_route_timeout* interval.

5.2.11 Link Failure

A neighbor of node X is considered active for a routing table entry if the neighbor sent a packet within *active_route_timeout* interval which was forwarded using that entry. Neighboring nodes periodically exchange hello message. When the next hop link in a routing table entry breaks, all

active neighbors are informed. Link failures are propagated by means of Route Error (RERR) messages, which also update destination sequence numbers.

5.2.12 Route Error

When node X is unable to forward packet P (from node S to node D) on link (X,Y), it generates a RERR message. Node X increments the destination sequence number for D cached at node X. The incremented sequence number N is included in the RERR. When node S receives the RERR, it initiates a new route discovery for D using destination sequence number at least as large as N . When node D receives the route request with destination sequence number N , node D will set its sequence number to N , unless it is already larger than N .

VI ROUTING SUMMARY

6.1 Protocols

- Typically divided into proactive, reactive and hybrid
- Plenty of routing protocols. Discussion here is far from exhaustive

6.2 Performance Studies

- Typically studied by simulations using ns, discrete event simulator
- Nodes (1030) remains stationary for pause time seconds (0900s) and then move to a random destination (1500m X300m space) at a uniform speed (020m/s). CBR traffic sources (430 packets/sec, 641024 bytes/packet)
- Attempt to estimate latency of route discovery, routing overhead ...

6.3 Actual tradeoff depends a lot on traffic and mobility patterns

- Higher traffic diversity (more sourcedestination pairs) increases overhead in on demand protocols
- Higher mobility will always increase overhead in all protocols

Roaming Node Scenario – Ping Traffic

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